

From Being a Resettlement Area to Tourist Destination? The Urban Growth and Tourism Development of the City of San Jose Del Monte, Bulacan, Philippines

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Abstract: San Jose del Monte, Philippines, has been a resettlement area for decades and is now one of the country's most highly urbanized cities, aiming to offer tourist destinations, but not enough research has been conducted to acknowledge and analyze the city's historical progress and development. After reviewing previous research about the resettlement area of San Jose del Monte and other reports in the city, the main contention of this study is the urban growth and tourism development of San Jose del Monte, which resulted from population growth, history, the economy and financial market, tourism, and some infrastructure projects made by the public and private sectors. The study also used the stakeholder's theory to identify, categorize, and analyze their powers. With that, it is found out that the urban transformation of the city from being a resettlement area to a tourist destination is a result of different efforts and manifestations brought by the government, entrepreneurs, religious organizations, residents, and tourists. The study also included recommendations for the government as well as for future researchers.

Keywords: History, Urban Growth, Resettlement, Tourism Development, Tourism Stakeholders, Interdisciplinary.

I. INTRODUCTION

In a developing country and tourist destination like the Philippines, urban growth and development thrive exponentially, putting emphasis on how important "urban planning" is to achieve sustainable urban development and urban tourism. Niazi et al. (2022) claims that there are economic, social, and financial contributions urban tourism makes to a city through having different attractions, may they be historical, cultural, environmental, or infrastructures such as museums, tombs, monuments, theaters, sports stadiums, parks, town halls, shopping malls, or religious sites. Correspondingly, Supriyadi (2019) claims that developments in infrastructure can serve as a tourist destination. With that, urban planning is much needed. Raghunath (2020) explicitly claimed months after moving to Manila, the capital of the Philippines, that the pandemic caused by COVID-19 has highlighted the value of urban planning and the necessity of equitable city administration.

According to the report by Delos Reyes et al. (2018), urban planning in the Philippines is a shared duty of multiple levels of government, from national to local. They also stated that the local government unit must carry more responsibility for achieving urban development and addressing urbanization challenges. Given that the local unit of the government carries greater responsibility in achieving urban development, this research focuses on one of the most highly urbanized cities in the province of Bulacan, the City of San Jose del Monte.

By investigating various past research regarding the City of San Jose del Monte, and as well as reviewing reports that discuss events in the city, the study seeks to gather data in order to create knowledge and perspectives pertaining to the relationship of population growth, tourism, and urban development in the city. The purpose of this study does not only aspire to contribute to the existing knowledge but also seeks to recommend infrastructure projects that the researcher see appropriate for the city tourism and the image of the city as the Rising City and as the Balcony of the Metropolis. The researcher also recommended further research about San Jose del Monte.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

History and the Guinness World Record of San Jose del Monte

The name of the municipality originated in the early 18th century when huntsmen from Meycauayan found a statue of Saint Joseph in the area where the mountains of Sierra Madre can be seen clearly and reported their discovery to the parish priest of Meycauayan. Since then, the statue has been called Saint Joseph of the Mountain, or in Spanish, San Jose del Monte. The founding of the municipality did not take place until March 2, 1752, two years after a decree on creating new municipalities from the Archbishop of Manila was announced in Lagulo Church in Meycauayan. The list of families who volunteered to be relocated was included in the decree. Therefore, the first relocation to San Jose del Monte was in the 18th century. At the time of the Spanish Colonial Period, reduction was widely applied. It is when municipalities with more population will undergo population reduction and will be relocated. The main objective, however, is to spread Catholicism (Official Gazette, n.d.-b).

On the other hand, another old document shows the other name of the municipality, or conceivably how other people call the area. The other document was written by Don Ramon Jordana y Morera entitled "Memoria Sobre la Producción de los Montes Publicos de Filipinas en el Año Económico de 1871-1872: Elevada al Excelentísimo Señor Ministro de Ultramar". There, he mentions the municipality as "Los Montes de San Jose" which roughly translates into English as "The Mountains of Saint Joseph". Conversely, others shortly called San Jose del Monte as San Jose such as Adolfo Puya Ruiz, the author of "Filipinas, Descripción General de la provincia de Bulacan: acompañada de un plano del Territorio que la misma ocupa"; and the *Ilustración Filipina*, a Spanish language magazine from 1859-1860 (Puya-Ruiz, 1888; Imprenta y Litografía Ramírez y Giraudier, 1860).

Other than the etymology of the San Jose del Monte and the history that paved the way for the establishment of city, the local government has also been making history for the city. An effort has been made on September 19, 2017 to set the Largest Lantern Parade in the world with 14, 173 eco-friendly lanterns brought by people of different ages in the city in which ended up successfully. Another effort also was made on December 20, 2019 in which the city bagged another Guinness world record having the greatest number of living figures in Nativity scene with 2,101 participants comprised of people dressed as Mary, Joseph, Jesus, angels, wise men, shepherds, and livestock (Balbin, 2019). To have a Guinness world record is not just an achievement but can also serve as tourism strategy or a platform for promotion (Rhythmia, 2023). In relation with that, Kingsley (2018) reported in detail how tourism developed in Nazaré, Portugal, after Garrett McNamara become a Guinness world record holder in 2012 in which he surfed a 78-foot wave, and after Maya Gabeira becomes another Guinness world record holder in 2015 for biggest wave ever surfed by a woman. Furthermore, the report stated the increase in visitors which rose from 40,000 in 2014 to more than 220,000 in 2018. Nevertheless, in the case of San Jose del Monte, there are no intensive studies yet to prove how being a Guinness world record holder help boost the tourism.

Population Growth in San Jose del Monte

The only inhabitants of the area before it became the municipality of San Jose del Monte were the indigenous communities of Itas and Dumagats. However, after becoming a municipality, the population is said to be less than 200 people, which was composed of family members of farmers and stonemasons in Libtong and Meycauayan due to relocation and reduction that transpired. *Ilustración Filipina* (1860) revealed that San Jose had a total population of 1713 in 1859, of which there were 773 native taxpayers and 112 mestizo taxpayers. Another old document reveals that San Jose del Monte in 1887 had a total population of 2,760, of which 1,422 were men and 1,338 were women (United States Bureau of Insular Affairs, 1902). However, the PhilAtlas (n.d.) provided data showing the population in the City of San Jose del Monte, which started on March 2, 1903, as shown in the Table 1.

TABLE I. Showing Census date, Population, and Growth Rate in 117 years (Retrieved from PhilAtlas, n.d.)

Census date	Population	Growth rate
1903 Mar 2	1,378	–
1918 Dec 31	3,141	5.34%
1939 Jan 1	5,826	3.14%
1948 Oct 1	5,363	-0.85%
1960 Feb 15	9,329	4.99%
1970 May 6	18,704	7.04%
1975 May 1	59,021	25.93%
1980 May 1	90,732	8.98%
1990 May 1	142,047	4.59%
1995 Sep 1	201,394	6.76%
2000 May 1	315,807	10.13%
2007 Aug 1	439,090	4.65%
2010 May 1	454,553	1.27%
2015 Aug 1	574,089	4.54%
2020 May 1	651,813	2.71%

In 2000, according to the National Statistics Office (2003), San Jose del Monte was the leading city in terms of population size and had the highest population growth rate among other cities and municipalities at 10.11 percent. The only cities at that time were Malolos and San Jose del Monte. Malolos converted into a city on October 8, 2002, under Republic Act 8754, while San Jose del Monte converted into a city on September 10, 2000, under Republic Act 8797 (Philippine Statistics Authority, 2017). On the other hand, the city is as proclaimed as highly-urbanized city by the Former President Rodrigo Duterte in 2020 under Proclamation 1057, in compliance with Republic Act 7160 Section 452, also known as the Local Government Code of 1991. The law states that for a city to be recognized and classified as a highly urbanized city, it should have at least 200,000 inhabitants and an average annual income of at least 50 million pesos over the previous two years (De la Cruz, 2020). In 2020, the City of San Jose del Monte has a population of 651,813, biggest in numbers compared to other cities and municipalities in Bulacan (Philippine Statistics Authority, 2022).

History of Relocation to San Jose del Monte

Mayor Arthur Robes, when he was still a congressman, claimed that the city had established a reputation as the relocation capital of Central Luzon (Reyes-Estropo, 2013). Contrary to the aforementioned first relocation to San Jose del Monte in the previous section, Balabo (2013) marked that the beginning of the relocation to the area of San Jose del Monte was when a typhoon forced families of retired soldiers to flee their homes in the outskirts of Taguig and Makati City and relocate them to Sapang Palay in 1959. He also claimed that a larger wave of relocation began on December 3, 1963, when then-Manila Mayor Antonio Villegas demolished the squats in Intramuros and the affected families were moved to Sapang Palay. Contrarily, Santiago (1977) revealed that what actually occurred was that the city administration failed to coordinate with the relevant national government agencies prior to the relocation, which led to the families and their belongings being literally dumped from Intramuros to Sapang Palay, which was not prepared to receive them.

In addition, there was an executive order released in 1967 that established the “Central Institute for the Training and Relocation of Urban Squatters” in Sapang Palay, tasked with researching the issues of urban squatting and developing solutions, or with rehabilitating, relocating, and training urban squatters on 100 hectares of land (Official Gazette, n.d.-a) that later became a barangay according to Bagong Buhay G Elementary School (n.d.). According to Lamberte and Bunda (1988), Sapang Palay was at the time the poorest resettlement area in the country, covering 752 hectares. The researchers further revealed that of the nine portions that make up Sapang Palay—areas A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, and I—area H was the most developed since it was intended to "showcase" the project, and that area G was the least developed at the time. Reyes-Estropo (2015), on the other hand, wrote in her article that in the 1970s, the national government remained committed to relocating squatter houses to Bulacan, which eventually resulted in the establishment of Liberty Farm, Pabahay 2000, Towerville, Gaya-Gaya, and San Jose Heights.

According to the Special Committee Report (1968), a relocation program is a complicated operation that shouldn't only concentrate on moving people, as was the case on December 3, 1963, when squatter families from Intramuros were dumped

at Sapang Palay. The study listed five main crucial issues, including the following: (1) a source of income in the new location that is at least as good as the one the squatter or slum dweller had before; (2) in the absence of an immediate source of income, a cheap and practical method of getting from one's place of employment to another; (3) adequate facilities, such as roads, water, medical services, waste disposal, and others; and (4) provisions for new housing.

However, Reyes (1996) reported that former Bulacan governor Roberto Pagdanganan appealed to Metro Manila mayors to be responsible in providing livelihood first before relocating their squatters to Bulacan in order to prevent crime incidents such as what occurred in San Jose del Monte after assimilating thousands of squatters from Metro Manila. The former governor also stated that the majority of criminal incidences in San Jose del Monte happened due to a lack of employment or job opportunities.

Real Estate Development in San Jose del Monte

One of the key contributors to the urban development of San Jose del Monte by having an investment and business-friendly destination, other than the population growth, is the real estate development. The city is currently the place where business tycoons such as Ayala, Araneta, and Villar Group of Companies invest through real estate development (Gonzales, 2022a; Gonzales, 2022b; Loyola, 2023). To support this claim, Hinojoza-Castro et al. (2022) identified that real estate developers are one of the principal stakeholders in urban development, similar to what happened in the Henares Corridor in Spain. On the other hand, Anthony and Vanessa Boanada-Fuchs (2022) detailed other roles of real estate developers in urban development, which span from political, legislative, and administrative matters to construction agendas.

With that, the Manila Bulletin (2022) reported in detail the developmental plans called Aspen on the 38-hectare land by the Vista Estate in the city. The name Aspen comes from a famous and tourist destination town located in Colorado, United States. Included in the plan are hotels, workplaces, dining areas, a health and wellness center, and an all-day supermarket. The architectural style incorporated in the plans, as can be seen in figures 1, 2, 3, and 4, was based on the actual architectural style found in Aspen, Colorado, United States.

Fig. 1. Architectural Perspective showing different facilities in Aspen.
(Photo from Manila Bulletin, 2022)

Fig. 2. Architectural Perspective showing the concept for food and retail stores.
(Photo from Manila Bulletin, 2022)

Fig. 3. Architectural Perspective showing the concept for Dining Area.
(Photo from Manila Bulletin, 2022)

Fig. 4. Architectural Perspective showing the concept for recreational spots.
(Photo from Manila Bulletin, 2022)

Tourism in San Jose del Monte

The study of Niazi et al. (2022) suggests that tourist attractions can be historical, cultural, environmental, or infrastructures, in which all can drive economic development in an area. Correspondingly, Yehia (2019) stated that some of the benefits of hosting a tourist destination include boosting the revenue of the local economy in which contributes to infrastructure projects of the government, and as well as creates profitable opportunities for local citizens. Currently, the City of San Jose del Monte is not just a resettlement area anymore but also a tourist destination.

With that, one of the most visited landmarks in the city is the Our Lady of Lourdes Grotto-Shrine, especially every Holy Week. It is a replica of the original Our Lady of Lourdes Grotto in France. It was opened to the public on February 11, 1965, and since then it has been visited by thousands of devotees. Some attractions to be found by tourists and by faithfuls in the grotto-shrine are Calvary Hill, where there are 14 Stations of the Cross that depict the agony of Jesus Christ; the 127 statues displayed in dioramas that took three years to build; and the Rosary Hill, where 155 very large concrete beads weighing over eight tons are located (Samonte, 2022). Another religious site that attracts devotees during the Lenten season is the heritage church, St. Joseph the Worker Parish, built in the 18th century, and the Padre Pio Mountain of Healing. In a statement from Rep. Florida robes, as reported by Rita (2023), over a million tourists were expected to visit the city during the 2023's Holy Week. This assumption is based on previous data that there were only 84,000 tourists in 2021 during the pandemic, and there were 1.2 million tourists in 2022 as the pandemic eased. Besides, Samonte (2019) reported that Our Lady of Lourdes Grotto had 1.5 million devotees that came from Metro Manila and neighboring provinces in 2019, so it is conceivable to have over millions of visitors during 2023's Holy Week in which corresponds with what Rep. Florida Robes stated in a recent report.

Other than religious sites, there are also numerous attractions, such as resorts, to be visited in the city. Mariano (2022), a travel enthusiast and a blogger, listed some resorts and events places to be visited in San Jose del Monte, Bulacan, which are Liora's Events Place, Casa Editha, 8 Farms Events Place, Villa Antonio de Dave Resort and Leisure Farm, and Casa Eugenia Private Resort. In addition, Kwyzer (2020) also listed some, such as Los Arcos de Hermano, D'Charkool Hauz Leisure Garden, Mariners Haven Resort and Event Place, Villa Leonora Resort and Event Place, and Grotto Vista Resort. Furthermore, there are more resorts than that to be visited in the city, such as Casa Aurelia, Villa Bardos Resorts and Events,

Sam's Inn and Events Place, Paradise Adventure Camp and Resort, and La Jardin, as listed by Top10place (n.d.). Tapawan et al. (2020) proved that the direct economic impact of the resort industry is the potential to generate jobs, while the indirect impact is the possibility to drive-in other job opportunities and investments in the area.

Other than resorts as tourist destinations in the city, some infrastructure projects led by the local government that will very likely boost tourism, generate job opportunities, and other local economic activities in the city, are the Riverpark Esplanade, which was unveiled to the public on February 14, 2023 (Palmero, 2023; Quismorio, 2023); the Rising Heart (Cervantes, 2020); the Convention Center, and the Rising City Hotel (The Philippine Star, 2023); and the "I Love AR SJDM" and view deck located in Brgy. Kaypian (Pedrajas, 2021). Meanwhile, there are also natural tourist attraction in the area in which are Mt. Balagbag and Kaytitinga Falls (Alcuezar, 2022). Whereas other tourist destinations, such as major shopping centers in the city, are the SM San Jose del Monte (Camus, 2016) and Starmall San Jose del Monte (Gonzales, 2022). Having shopping centers in the city is important for local tourism. Rodriguez et al. (2020) claimed that shopping tourism is one of the leading strategies for tourism development and improving the local economy in urban areas.

For the moment, one of the potential tourist attractions in the city is the ABS-CBN Sound Stage, which was inaugurated on December 12, 2018. It is reported that the sound stages will help the network provide an international level of production (ABS-CBN News, 2018). While according to Chanco (2022), the idea behind the ABS-CBN Sound Stage is to have a Filipino version of Universal Studios. However, things went slowly after the network's franchise was denied. If the ABS-CBN Sound Stage be completed and offer studio tours and experiences as what they have already been doing in ABS-CBN compound since 1997 (ABS-CBN, 2020), then it will certainly attract local and foreign tourists in the city as well. If the ABS-CBN Sound Stage will live to its expectation, therefore it will be similar to other international studios in Hollywood such as Warner Brothers or Warner Bros., Sony Pictures, Paramount Pictures, and Universal Studios, which also offers studio tours (Richards, 2016). Bastien and Associates, Inc., the designer of the ABS-CBN Sound Stage also designed other film and Television studios in which among their famous projects are Sony Pictures and Paramount Pictures – Generoddenberry Building (Bastien and Associates, Inc., n.d.).

Transportation System Development

Transportation can be used as an indicator for urban development, similar to what Kishue et al. (2003) argued in their study, which focused on Cebu City. The City of San Jose del Monte, on the other hand, had developments pertaining to transportation systems. Lamberte & Bunda (1988) revealed that the mode of transportation in the late 1980s in San Jose del Monte were only tricycles and jeepneys. There were also buses bound to Novaliches and Sta. Maria. On tricycles, the fare ranges from Php1 to Php5 depending on the kilometer length and the interiority of the place, while jeepney fare costs at least Php1.

In the present time, there are already new and developing modes of transportation other than jeepneys and buses that connect the city to its other cities and municipalities. As the local government complies with the national government's campaign of transport modernization that will make public transportation safer, more comfortable, and more eco-friendly, there were 16 modern public utility vehicles, also known as e-jeepneys, turned over by Isuzu Philippines Corporation to connect the city to Sta. Maria and Meycauayan in 2019, and 20 new modern jeepneys were presented by Sapang Palay Grotto Transport Service Cooperative and served passengers in 2021. The Sapang Palay Grotto Transport Service Cooperative is the eighth transport cooperative to comply with the modernization program in the city. (Tecson, 2022; Mauricio, 2020). On the other hand, another developing mode of transportation is the 22-kilometer railway line of Metro Rail Transit Line 7 (MRT 7), with 14 stations, that will connect the city of San Jose del Monte to Quezon City. It is expected that, when completed, the travel time of more than 300,000 commuters will be reduced on a larger scale (Camus, 2021).

Economic Development and Financial Activities

Lamberte & Bunda (1988) revealed in their study that there was no market in Sapang Palay at the early stages of the resettlement project of which took place years and even decades before the 1980s. However, an 8, 693 square meter market was soon called Sampol Market was established after years of being an area where trading of goods and flocking of vendors takes place. The etymology of 'Sampol' comes from the Sample Barangay post that was no longer in existence in the 1980s. The authors also added the survey conducted by the National Housing Authority in 1982, where Sampol Market was found to have 191 stalls comprised of different sections such as a fish section, a meat section, a meat and chicken section, a vegetable section, a variety section, a dress section, an eatery section, a dry goods section, a candy section, a cooked food section, a stock room, a recreational center, school supplies, a beauty shop and parlor, a snack store, refreshment store,

magazine stand, eggs section, poultry supply, fruit stand, drugstore, bakery, The authors also stated that commercial and trading activities were not confined to the market, given that other markets started to operate in succeeding years.

Reyes (1996), on the other hand, revealed in her report that there were insufficient employment opportunities in San Jose del Monte due to decades of resettlement projects, which resulted in an increase in the crime rate in the area and also in Bulacan. Lamberte & Bundo (1988) revealed in their study that only a few household heads were employed in the resettlement site, while others were able to continue working in Manila. The authors also revealed that some relocatees work as craftsmen; some are production-process and related workers; some work in the transport, communication, and service industry; while the rest were agricultural workers, clerical workers, and laborers. The authors further revealed that some relocatees were self-employed given the insufficient employment opportunities in the resettlement site, and the costly fare of transportation if they chose to still work in Metro Manila.

Lamberte & Bundo (1988) also divulged in their study that there were no formal financial institutions in Sapang Palay, whereas banks were an hour away. This implies that there were no banks in San Jose del Monte in early 1980's and years behind. With that, the researchers identified the manifestations of informal moneylenders also known as "5/6"; the rotating saving and credit association (ROSCAS) which can be understood easily by the locals as "paluwagan"; and the traders/suppliers in which most were called "Bombay" or East Indians. For those people joining paluwagans, the researchers identified nine reasons in which are: (1) to raise funds for household consumption; (2) to raise funds to finance business; (3) to pay old debts; (4) to avoid borrowing from moneylenders; (5) to raise fund for lending to others; (6) to raise funds to buy home appliances, furniture, and fixtures; (7) to raise funds to repair or improve the house; (8) to raise funds to apply for a job abroad; and (9) to save money.

One of the known rotating save and credit cooperatives in San Jose del Monte is the San Jose KOOP, which was registered on May 14, 1987, in the Bureau of Cooperatives, re-registered as a credit cooperative on January 3, 1992, in the Cooperative Development Authority, and re-registered on February 9, 1993, with a new corporate name as San Jose del Monte Kilusang Bayan sa Kaunlara, Inc. In the present, the corporate name that is currently registered is San Jose del Monte Savings and Credit Cooperative (San Jose KOOP, n.d.). The San Jose KOOP in 2017 has entered the Top 50 Cooperatives in the Billionaire Bracket of the Cooperative Development Authority for having Php1.66 billion together with three other cooperatives in the province of Bulacan (Balbin, 2018).

Other than that, there were only few other succeeding evidences that constitutes economic activities and development in the city. Camus (2016) reported that 62 percent of households living in San Jose del Monte have family members working overseas. There are already numerous studies that prove how remittances of overseas Filipino workers help the economy afloat. Kang and Latoja (2022) claimed that migrant workers who meet their financial goals in the host country are more likely to return; effective reintegration also allows these returnees to contribute to the local economy through domestic work and entrepreneurial endeavors.

Apart from that, Grunewald (2006) argued that poverty rate and economy are intertwined by considering the impact of economic growth to job opportunities and income growth. With that, according to Philippine Statistics Authority (2021), the poverty incidence of San Jose del Monte in 2018 was 4.6 percent. Although the poverty incidence in National Capital Region is 3.5 percent (Mercado, 2022), it is conceivable how relatively low percentage compared to other cities and municipalities that ranges between 10 percent and 60 percent. This also suggest a higher proportion of people living in San Jose del Monte to have higher standard of living. Palatino (2022) also pointed out the difference and the poverty gap between cities and rural areas which means that many people residing in cities such as San Jose del Monte have higher standard of living than people residing in rural areas. Clearly, if higher proportion of people residing in San Jose del Monte have higher standard of living, therefore, the per capita income or the amount of money being earned by the city residents are relatively higher compared to others. And with that, taxes collected from the residents are higher.

Given that, the tax revenue in San Jose del Monte contributes to annual regular income of the city. According to PhilAtlas (n.d.), yearly regular income is calculated as the total of locally received revenue, internal revenue allotment (IRA) current year, and additional shares from national tax collection. Locally generated revenue, on the other hand, is the total of various taxes (both real estate and commercial), regulatory fees, service charges, and earnings from economic operations. The yearly recurring income given by PhilAtlas (n.d.) in San Jose del Monte began in 2009 and ended in 2016. The yearly regular revenue in 2009 was Php656,305,202.28, while it was Php1,189,382,184.07 in 2016. The rise was 81.22% in 8 years.

TABLE II. Data showing Annual Income and Changes in Rate per Fiscal Year (Retrieved from PhilAtlas, n.d.)

Fiscal Year	Annual Regular Income	Change
2009	656,305,202.28	–
2010	718,668,530.38	9.50%
2011	783,943,135.50	9.08%
2012	727,208,075.99	-7.24%
2013	1,031,604,786.81	41.86%
2014	974,388,179.32	-5.55%
2015	1,078,619,971.16	10.70%
2016	1,189,382,184.07	10.27%

III. METHODOLOGY

This study was largely qualitative in approach and used less quantitative data that only arises from sources and related literature. Correspondingly, the stakeholder’s theory has been used to analyze what and who contributes to tourism development. Furthermore, in stakeholder theory, there were three steps: first, identification of stakeholders; second, categorization of stakeholders; and third, stakeholder prioritization. After identifying the stakeholders based on observations, the researcher started categorizing them by drawing a table showing the roles, manifestations, and types of stakeholders. Tractivity (n.d.) revealed different types of stakeholders in which are the key stakeholders, primary stakeholders, and secondary stakeholders. In addition, a four-quadrant model was used to map out the power and interest of the stakeholders in tourism development after categorization. This study draws discussion, results, and conclusions from related literature as well as direct observations of various tourist destinations in the city.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

By using stakeholder theory, direct observation, and a literature review, the study identified five stakeholders in tourism development in San Jose del Monte. The Table III shows the type, role, and manifestations of stakeholders. The type represents the importance and influence of the stakeholder. The role shows the responsibility. While the manifestations are the accomplishments and or the progress.

It is evident that the local government is the key stakeholder in order to make the city not just a resettlement area but, more importantly, a tourist destination as well. The local government holds great power, responsibility, influence, and importance. Every move they make may greatly affect other stakeholders in tourism. Nevertheless, the local government is the one that formulates infrastructure projects that intend tourism beautification within the city and as well as hands over permits like business permits and construction permits to other stakeholders. Among the manifestations of the local government, the researcher observed how Riverpark Esplanade, located in Brgy. Dulong Bayan, has attracted visitors that seek relaxation, socialization, exercise, and contemplation more than any other parks in the city. The researcher also noted that more people preferred visiting the Riverpark Esplanade than the People’s Park located in Brgy. Sapang Palay Proper. The researcher also noticed new vendors near the Riverpark Esplanade. Originally, there were only food and convenience stores nearby; eventually, food carts emerged, serving street foods and beverages.

Apart from that, entrepreneurs play vital roles in tourism development in the city. They are primary stakeholders, for they can be affected by the decisions of the key stakeholder, which is the government. They generate employment opportunities, raise infrastructures, offer services such as wellness and leisure activities and food experiences, attract other investors such as competitors that benefit the tourism sector, and contribute to the local economy through direct and indirect impacts, similar to the case of resorts in Dasmariñas City, Cavite, studied by Tapawan et al. (2020). Furthermore, the researcher also noted and identified that one of the leading entrepreneurs in the city were the real estate developers, given the numerous existing different subdivisions. Besides, Ignacio (2023) reported how real estate will continue to thrive even after economic disruptions. In addition to that, the researcher also noted that restaurant owners are also entrepreneurs. In the city, there were some prominent restaurants to visit for tourists who were not looking for fast-food restaurants.

On the other hand, the religious organization has been considered by the researcher, based on observation, as a secondary stakeholder. This is due to the fact that religions and faith communities invite their followers and devotees to visit their religious site for spiritual activities and not for leisure. Thus, the faithful and believers visit the city during a religious

activity of their religion only for spiritual enlightenment and experience. Although these religious tourists and visitors' primary objective is to attend religious activity, they still contribute to generating income for eateries, fine dining restaurants, and fast-food chains.

Tourists and visitors are another stakeholder in tourism development who, after the local government, are the second most important stakeholder. They are the target markets for entrepreneurs, the city tourism office, and the local government itself in terms of tourism, other than the residents or local community. Tourists spend money in restaurants, shopping malls, stores, leisure, and accommodations, which all contribute to economic development in the city. Moreover, many tourists share their experience with others, especially those who consider themselves to be bloggers and vloggers. Mandigma et al. (2022) studied that travel vloggers affect tourism in a way that they influence others by providing information and raising expectations on a certain destination or attraction. Thus, their viewers desire to travel to a certain destination is being uplifted.

After everything else, the last stakeholder are the residents. The researcher deemed to consider the residents as secondary stakeholders because they are affected by tourism in the city less than the other stakeholders of tourism development. One line that connects the residents to tourism development is economic development. If the local economy progresses, this will lead to job opportunities as well as an increase in income. The other line that connects the residents to tourism development is the maintenance and preservation of tourist destinations and attractions in the city. The local residents are deemed to be considered visitors as well, and they are expected to preserve the cleanliness of the place when visiting a tourist destination or attraction. Preserving cleanliness in the city is a shared responsibility of the community and the local government. With that, the residents are as important as the other tourists and visitors from other cities, provinces, or even foreign countries. In addition to that, some residents do have relatives outside the city. The residents provide tourist destination and attraction information to their relatives, thus attracting their relatives to visit and tour the city, which is how the referral system works.

TABLE III. The type, role, and manifestations of Stakeholders found in research area.

STAKEHOLDERS	TYPE	ROLES	MANIFESTATIONS
Local Government	Key stakeholder	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Formulate and implement tourism policies. 2. Build infrastructures for tourism purposes. 3. Support other stakeholders. 4. Encourage investors and entrepreneurs 5. Inform, invite, and welcome target market. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Public Parks 2. View Decks 3. Rising City Hotel 4. Convention Center 5. Sports Stadium 6. Sidewalk plants and tree planting projects 7. Roads and Bridges
Entrepreneurs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Restaurant Owners • Real Estate Developers • Resort Owners • Wellness and recreational center owners • Shopping Mall owners • Store owners • School owners 	Primary Stakeholder	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Provide hotel, residential building, lodging houses, wellness and leisure activities, and local food experience. 2. Attracts investors, provide employment opportunities, and helps local economy. 3. Inform, invite, and welcome target market. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Resorts and Events Places 2. Residential Housing 3. Shopping Malls 4. Restaurants 5. Educational Institutions 6. Wellness and Recreational Centers 7. Leisure Areas
Religious Organization <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Catholic Church 	Secondary Stakeholder	Invite and welcome faithfuls and believers during Lenten season and other religious activities.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Churches 2. Religious sites

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Christian/ Protestant Churches • Islam 			
Tourists <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visitors • Foreigners • Vloggers • Bloggers 	Primary Stakeholder	Raise awareness and provide tourism destination information among other travelers, visitors, and relatives.	1. Social Media Publicity 2. Referral System
Residents <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Old Tenants (Natives) • Relocatees 	Secondary Stakeholder	Raise awareness and provide tourism destination information among other travelers, visitors, and relatives.	1. Social Media Publicity 2. Referral System

Graph 1. Power/ Influence Matrix of Stakeholders in terms of Tourism Development

In Graph 1, the stakeholders are being analyzed and mapped out using four-quadrant matrix depending on their power and interest in tourism development. Consequently, the government was placed in quadrant 1 given their high level of power and interest over tourism development in the city. The government has been spending resources for infrastructure tourism, inform residents and tourists, and collaborate with entrepreneurs. On the other hand, the entrepreneurs were placed in quadrant 2 for the reason that they do have power in terms of resources and connection with the government but they do have less interest in tourism since their primary objective is making profit. This doesn't mean that they have no interest in tourism. They do have interest in tourism since they will make profit from tourism. Conversely, the religious organizations were placed in quadrant 3 for the reason that they do not have power and interest in tourism development in the city. Still, they do have power over their followers but they do not have power over the government and entrepreneurs that is why they are placed a little bit above the residents and the tourists. Lastly, the tourists and residents were placed in quadrant 4 since they do have high interest in tourism development in the city, however they do not have enough power similar to the

government. It is also important to take note that the residents have higher power over the tourist, contrarywise, the tourists have higher interest over the residents.

V. CONCLUSION

Through this study, it was found out that the City of San Jose del Monte, Bulacan, had histories of resettlement projects. Although reduction during the Spanish colonization resulted in the relocation of some residents of Meycauayan to San Jose del Monte, it is more accurate to conclude that the first relocation, due to unfortunate events and conditions, was started in 1959, which was followed by many more resettlement projects over the years and decades led by the government. The resettlement projects that transpired in the city resulted in fast population growth. Thus, the city did not only gain a greater number of residents but also workers and tax payers, which eventually led San Jose del Monte to its cityhood and to the proclamation of being a highly urbanized city. Given these developments, the transport system progressed as well in order to satisfy transportation needs of the people in which could also be used for tourism activities. Apart from that, it was also found out that the city can be considered a tourist destination given the number of tourists visiting the city in annual basis, as well as given the tourism development that manifested through economic, social, environmental, and infrastructure development spearheaded by the local government and with the help of primary and secondary stakeholders.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The researcher recommends conducting in-depth qualitative and/or quantitative research that will discuss the perceptions, awareness, and desire of the relocatees, old tenants, and government officials towards the transition of the city from being a resettlement area to a tourist destination.
2. The researcher recommends conducting in-depth qualitative and/or quantitative research that focuses on the urbanization, gentrification, and sustainable development of the city.
3. The researcher recommends conducting in-depth qualitative and/or quantitative research that utilizes the other stakeholder theory's salience model for classifying stakeholders in tourism and urban development in the city, as well as theories like spatial development theory, placemaking theory, social development theory, and system theory.

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